

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D1.2 Initial Data Management Plan

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
AOI	Area of Interest
API	Application Programming Interface
CDI	Common Data Index
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
CSV	Comma-separated values
DC	Data cube
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DS	Dataset
EC	European Council
EEA	European Environment Agency
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
EVER-EST	European Virtual Environment for Research – Earth Science Themes
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GC	Grand challenge
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GeoJSON(-LD)	Geographical JavaScript Object Notation (Linked Data)
GeoTIFF	Geographic Tagged Image File Format
GES	Good Environmental Status
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
InSAR	Interferometric synthetic aperture radar
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NetCDF CF	Network Common Data Form (Climate and Forecast)
NOOA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PAR	Photosynthetically Active Radiation
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RO	Research Object
ROHub	Research Object hub
SAR	Synthetic aperture radar
SC	Scenario
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
SWEET	Semantic Web for Earth and Environment Technology
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VPR	Volcanic Plume Retrieval
WAV	Wave form audio format

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an initial version of the RELIANCE data management plan (DMP), following the template provided by the European Commission in the Participant Portal. The document outlines data that will be collected or generated during the project and discusses how it will be handled during and after the project lifetime. As part of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), RELIANCE delivers a first version of the DMP at an early stage of the project. This first version focusses on already identified research data to be collected, used and/or produced by the project, particularly by our scientific communities as part of the implementation of their use cases, but also the user data collected by the RELIANCE services. Additional data or updated data to be used/produced by the use cases will be detailed in the public deliverable of the use cases D7.1 in M12, and accordingly the DMP will be updated. Similarly, the DMP will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, e.g., new data is used/produced. A final version of the DMP will be delivered at M24, which will include more detailed plan regarding external data sharing, use and exploitation after the end of the project. In addition to the official releases in the form of deliverables, the DMP is planned to be maintained in Argos, the EOSC service enabling the management of DMPs.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of good data management. As stated in the “Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020” [1], the European Commission encourages open access to and reuse of digital research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects through the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot), following FAIR data principles to make such data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Minimally, the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications should be openly accessible, but also any other data provided by the project is encouraged to follow the same guidelines. A description of such data should be provided in a Data Management Plan (DMP). Any project participating in the ORD pilot, such as RELIANCE, is required to submit a DMP, and according to the guidelines, a first version of such plan should be submitted within the first 6 months of the project. Moreover, the plan must be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise.

A H2020 project DMP, as stated in the participant portal of the EC, should describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated during the project lifetime. In particular, in order to make research FAIR, the DMP should include information on:

- the handling of research data during & after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology & standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated & preserved

The DMP should also provide information on the measures taken to safeguard and protect sensitive data.

RELIANCE will take into consideration, in particular, the Article 29.3 in the Grant Agreement (Open access to research data). According to the article project participants will have to provide information about data and relevant tools needed for the validation of project results. To this end, data must be stored in data repositories to make it available to third parties who should be able to access, mine, exploit and disseminate the data, free of charge for the user (according to a definition of the open research data).

It is important to note that the Commission also recognizes that there may be good reasons to keep some or even all research data generated in a project closed. Accordingly, the ORD pilot follows the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary", and states that the DMP should specify if certain datasets remain closed and the reasons for not giving access to it (e.g., risk to reach project goals).

This document presents the initial DMP of RELIANCE project, which follows the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP Template provided by the European Commission. A final version of the DMP will be delivered in M24. Moreover, the DMP is planned to be maintained in the EOSC service Argos¹, where the current version of the DMP will be kept with the latest changes/updates.

2.2 Audience

This deliverable is intended to offer guidance to data producers and/or data stewards, as well as data service providers involved in the project. In particular, this DMP is relevant for the scientific communities of the RELIANCE Consortium, which will collect, use and generate different types of data as part of the implementation of their use cases. Similarly, the DMP will be also useful for the technical partners of the RELIANCE Consortium, who will oversee and support the management of the data used by the scientific communities.

2.3 Structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

- Section 3 presents a general description of the initially identified datasets collected, used and produced by the RELIANCE project.
- Section 4 describes how such data would be identified, shared and discovered, made interoperable and reused.
- Section 5 presents the way of financing the DMP by the project.
- Section 6 discusses security and ethics considerations.
- Section 7 introduces the list of the initially identified datasets

3 Data Summary

RELIANCE project will handle two main types of data: i) research data, and ii) user data. The former concerns the access, re-use and preservation of research data generated during the research work, and it is the main focus of this data management plan in compliance with the Horizon 2020 Pilot on Open Research Data. The latter is concerned with data collected by the RELIANCE services, and in particular, the ROHub service where users create their account after logging in using any of the supported identity providers. Since ROHub is being integrated with the EGI check-in service, users will be able to use Single Sign On across RELIANCE services and other EOSC services. Once accounts are created, users may provide additional personal data to ROHub in addition to the data obtained from the identity provider, such as his description, preferences, tokens in other systems, etc. Such data and how it is handled is described in the ROHub privacy policy². ROHub requires the user to give his consent on the processing of his personal data and policy, in order to create his account.

Research data will be collected, used and/or produced within the project mostly by the scientific communities as part of the implementation of their use cases and scenarios. These include use cases

¹ <https://argos.openaire.eu/plans/overview/24a939db-f8fc-4864-bce9-924ea4887c17>

² <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/6a67fc42535f4582bdcc/>

vertical to each user community as well as an extended multidisciplinary research activity to analyse the consequences of the 2020 Lockdown on our environment (see more information below). Hence the primary purpose of such data is to enable these communities to carry out the processing, analyses and simulations necessary to produce the research results/outcomes that can address the scientific challenges identified. Moreover, the implementation of these use cases and scenarios will enable RELIANCE to validate and demonstrate its services and their value proposition (Project Objective 3).

Such data include various large Earth Observation datasets and products, in particular from Copernicus programme, as well as other data used for the analysis/simulations, along with the resulting datasets produced by those processes. Some example datasets are:

- Ocean Colour satellite data (Sentinel-3 OLCI)
- Raw wav files from hydrophone memories
- Sound Pressure Level (SPL) data (e.g., CSV files)
- Seafloor data
- Marine surface Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) (e.g., NetCDF files, raster)
- Photonic zones data (e.g., shapefiles)
- Coral datasets (coral sites in the Mediterranean Sea, fossil coral age, ...)
- Environmental datasets
- Simulation datasets (e.g., NetCDF files)
- InSAR multi-temporal data
- Volcanic Plume Retrieval (VPR) data
- Seismic data

Regarding the datasets/products generated as part of these scenarios, there are two main types particularly relevant in the RELIANCE context:

- Data cubes that enable efficient access and reuse of EO data subsets.
- Research objects that provide the overarching mechanism to manage the resources associated with the different research activities and to connect them as part of a complete research work or parts of it. Thus, regardless of the dataset type generated/used in a particular research work (as any other research product), they will be aggregated, managed and be accessible via the research object.

The detailed list of already identified datasets, and their source, is provided in Section 7. This list will be updated and complemented with further information (e.g., size) after the delivery of D7.1 at M12, which will provide a first official report of the use cases.

Regarding the reuse of existing data, RELIANCE will re-use several datasets, including various large Earth Observation datasets and products from Copernicus programme, as previously noted, but also several datasets of scientific (processed) data available in different domain specific or general-purpose repositories (e.g., PANGAEA, GitHub, Zenodo) or even from internal institutional databases. The data (and other results) produced by the scientific communities in RELIANCE will be managed via Research Objects, which will be stored in the public platform ROHub, but the resources themselves may be stored in ROHub too or in any other data storage service e.g., from EOSC (e.g., B2drop or Zenodo). Additionally, releases of the research objects may be also published via B2Share or Zenodo to be discoverable by a wider audience.

Regarding data utility, the data and research objects generated in RELIANCE will be highly valuable to other researchers and stakeholders, not only from Earth Science but also from other fields. For example, research objects produced by RELIANCE that could allow the systematic and repetitive measurement of e.g., usage of clean water, reduction in fertilizers, impacts on greenhouse gas

emission by using Copernicus Data, can help food companies in becoming leaders in clean/ fair production and technologies and in green economy, in line with the European Green Deal. Similarly, research objects allowing, for example, the systematic monitoring of environmental variable of interest, could support national or regional public administrations and authorities in their activities and decisions like the definition of sustainable and innovative strategies for tourism.

The case studies that are the main source (and owners) of data collected and generated within RELIANCE are shortly summarised below. A detailed description of these studies will be provided in D7.1 at M12.

3.1 Multidisciplinary case studies on 2020 lockdown

This use case aims to quantify the de-impact of the lockdown on the atmospheric and marine coastal environment, highlighting the role of open data and availability of pre-pandemic data, and post-pandemic data. The main objectives of this case study will be to: 1) test the evolution of the anthropogenic impact on the atmospheric and marine-coastal systems following the lockdown in Mediterranean areas with high urban and/or industrial density; 2) quantify in a synoptic way, the good environmental status of the sea (GES) at the end of the lockdown phase, by directly applying open data approach followed by further elaborations; 3) integrate measures from the observation sites within the scientific networks involved, adding (i) bespoke measures in hotspots subject to maximum change, (ii) qualitative evidence from observations of citizens according to the local ecological knowledge approach; 4) build a shared vision among different actors by engaging citizens of the mapped areas and relevant stakeholders, e.g. fishermen and/or health services, in data acquisition, interpretation and validation, as well as in the discussion on the project results and its perspectives.

Figure 1 S2-derived turbidity maps for the North Lagoon: A) February 20th, B) March 19th and C) April 15th 2020. Red dotted lines

3.2 Grand Challenge 1: Sea Pollution

To understand and quantify the impact of marine litter and to reduce its presence in the ocean is crucial to track the litter and plastic (micro and macro plastic), in particular, from sources to sinks. This multidisciplinary user case scenario investigates the role of physical and biological processes on transport, settling and accumulation of plastics in the marine environment, from the rivers to the sea. Hydrologic (in land) and oceanographic (coastal and open sea) modelling and remote sensing will help to estimate the river inputs and the distribution of litter in the water column and on the seabed and its impacts along the food web. This case study involves experts in meteorology, hydrology, physical oceanography, geophysics and biology.

Figure 2 Typology of macroscopic anthropogenic impacts in the Dohrn Canyon including litter and lost fishing gears

3.3 Grand Challenge 2: Loss of Biodiversity and Sustainability (Biodiversity, fisheries, marine litter)

This multidisciplinary case study targets those Mediterranean cold water coral habitats that develop under thermal conditions very close to 14 °C. Maps of the current cold water coral distribution in the Mediterranean Sea will be correlated to chemical and physical parameters (e.g., temperature, salinity, nutrients, dissolved oxygen concentration) from field data and modelling. The fossil records will be also analyzed through U/Th dating and isotopic geochemistry, and the abundance of fossil corals will be correlated to proxy-based environmental reconstructions. Possible future scenarios will be provided based on regional models (e.g., Med-CORDEX) and will focus on the increase of temperature and consequent cold-water coral habitat loss. The role of other parameters such as nutrient concentration and decreasing pH will be also investigated. This case study involves experts in paleoclimatology, paleoecology, physical and chemical oceanography, biology, ecology and modelling.

Figure 3 Water depth of the current Isotherm of 14 in the Mediterranean Sea. This value represents the thermal limit for cold water corals. In Red Cold water corals occurrences. Unpublished images. Courtesy of Paolo Montagna

3.4 Grand Challenge 3: Extreme weather events and climate adaptation (biomass)

This use case is going to 1) combine satellite data and in-situ observations with climate model outputs and global/regional re-analysis data to assess the extent of the Arctic browning, 2) characterize local trends, 3) investigate future scenarios, and 4) engage with local populations, among whom Sami reindeer herders (highly concerned and most vulnerable) and provide them with maps to better manage their pastures and migration since reindeer cannot feed when lichens are covered with a layer of ice.

Figure 4 Browning events: (a, b) extreme winter warming damage to *Empetrum nigrum* heathland in Sub-Arctic north-west Scandinavia; (c) icing damage to *Dryas octopetala* in High Arctic Svalbard; (d, e) frost drought damage to *Calluna*

3.5 Grand Challenge 4: Reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions

The first use case will study a twin Eyjafjallajokull (Iceland) 2010 eruption. Volcanic eruptions of this magnitude (Volcanic Explosivity Index 5-6) can impact global climate, reducing the amount of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface, lowering temperatures in the troposphere, and changing atmospheric circulation patterns. The particles and gases typically dissipate after about 2 years, but the effect is nearly global. This use case will focus in particular on tephra and ash dispersal and fallout from explosive volcanic eruptions, SO₂ clouds dispersal, and their interactions with the atmospheric and marine environments.

Figure 5 Eyjafjallajökull eruption – Iceland 2010. Detailed map of ash effective radius with the corresponding particle-size distribution showing three main mode

The second use case will study an explosive eruption at the Campi Flegrei (Italy) caldera. Comprehensive monitoring of volcanoes is vital in order to provide timely warnings of volcano reawakening. Early detection of unrest by means of remote sensing and in situ data, analyzed and interpreted by the scientific community, helps reduce socioeconomic losses. For that to happen it is necessary the timely completion of the scientific process of data collection, analysis and interpretation. This use case will address the need in the volcanological community, for technological tools and services which make this process faster and allow the dissemination of the research products for immediate societal benefit.

Figure 6 Mean surface deformation velocity of the Bay of Naples, computed using Sentinel-1 radar data from ESA acquired in 2014-2016

4 FAIR Data

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions of metadata

The datasets are internally identified using a simple naming convention:

- [Dataset_Type][Dataset_#]-GC[Grand_Challenge_#]-SC[Scenario_#]

Where Dataset_Type is a two-character acronym as follows:

- Data Cube: DC
- Research Object: RO
- Other type of dataset: DS

Number (Dataset_#, Grand_Challenge_# and Scenario_#) is a sequential integer, e.g., 1,2,3,...

Note1: the multidisciplinary case studies on 2020 lockdown will be identified as GC0.

Note2: as mentioned in Section 3, regardless of the dataset type (e.g., a data cube, a csv dataset, an image or any other dataset), they will be managed and be accessible via research objects (which can also aggregate other research objects), and as described next, each of them will have its own metadata, including the research object itself.

Moreover, the datasets and products (as any other artifact) generated by the use cases, which will be managed via research objects will have resolvable and permanent identifiers, as well as the research object itself. In particular, the naming convention is as follows:

- For a research object:
 - <https://w3id.org/ro-id/{uuid}>
- For a resource (e.g., data cube, dataset) aggregated by the research object:
 - <https://w3id.org/ro-id/{uuid1}/resources/{uuid2}>

Furthermore, releases/snapshots of a research objects may get a DOI from ROHub or from another EOSC data service/repositories like Zenodo or B2Share.

RELIANCE keep track of research object versions as part of the management of its lifecycle. In particular the releases/snapshots allow are revisions (versions) of the research object that can be generated at different points in time, keeping track of the previous version and the log of changes between them.

Regarding metadata of the datasets (re-)used it depends on the nature and type of the data, as well as on the source system/repository where this data is available. There are several relevant metadata standards for RELIANCE, which we have described and analysed. In particular, deliverable “D4.1-DataCube metadata model” provides a detailed analysis of relevant metadata standards for Earth Observation datasets, while “D5.1-RO Model adapted to EOSC” describes relevant specifications for the representation of research objects.

In short, the following general purpose metadata models have been identified as relevant, and will be partially supported by RELIANCE as needed:

- The OpenAIRE metadata model described in the OpenAIRE metadata guidelines for data archives.
- The ISO 19115 content model (used, for example, by NOAA’s National Centers for Environmental Information services).
- The ISO 19139 content model (used, for example, by the SeaDataNet Cruise Summary Report – CSR - and Common Data Index - CDI - services), which extends the previous one for INSPIRE-compliance.
- The schema.org/DataSet format (used, for example, by PANGAEA).
- NetCDF
- OGC OpenSearch Extension for Earth Observation
- OGC EO Dataset Metadata GeoJSON(-LD) Encoding, with its corresponding ontology

Similarly, relevant metadata models for Earth-Observation in general and community specific include:

- Metadata models for Copernicus missions: <https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/data-offer/inspire-compliant-metadata>

- The Semantic Web for Earth and Environment Technology (SWEET) ontology (<https://github.com/ESIPFed/sweet>), governed by the ESIP Semantic Technologies Committee, which is focused on the representation of many different types of concepts related to physical quantities, Earth realms, space, time, etc.
- The SeaDataNet Common Vocabularies: <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Common-Vocabularies>
- The SeaBASS oceanographic and atmospheric in-situ measurements vocabulary: <https://seabass.gsfc.nasa.gov/wiki/metadataheaders>
- Metadata associated to products related to radar data (e.g., SAR Data products developed by EPOS in the Thematic Core Service “Satellite Data” and cured mainly by IREA) for:
 - LOS_displacement time series
 - Unwrapped interferograms
 - Wrapped interferograms
- The NetCDF CF (Climate and Forecast) Conventions: <https://cfconventions.org/>. These are conventions designed to promote the processing and sharing of files created with the NetCDF API.

Finally, the relevant models analysed for research objects include the original Wf4Ever RO model specification (<http://wf4ever.github.io/ro/>), the EVER-EST RO model extensions (<https://github.com/wf4ever/ro/tree/earth-science>), and the newest RO-crate specification (<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>).

Based on the analysis of those models, RELIANCE proposed two main models:

- one for the description of data cubes products in RELIANCE, and
- one for the representation of research objects in RELIANCE.

The first one is a four-layers metadata model (described in detail in D4.1) including:

- **General metadata layer**, which allows representing general information about the digital object (data cube) and is aligned with the recommendations proposed by OpenAIRE (OpenAIRE metadata guidelines for Data Providers), and hence aligned with DataCite. The properties proposed for this layer are the following (in bold font those that are compulsory)³:
 - **Identifier** (identifier)
 - Alternate identifier (alternateIdentifiers/alternateIdentifier)
 - Related identifier (relatedIdentifiers/relatedIdentifier)
 - **Title** (title)
 - **ResourceType** (resourceType equal to Dataset, for the time being, although we will aim at generating a DataCube resource type in the future)
 - **Publication year** (publicationYear)
 - Description (descriptions/description)
 - Creation date (dct:created, dates/date [dateType=])
 - Modification date (dct:modified)
 - Publication date (dct:date)
 - Version (version)
 - Update frequency (dct:accrualPeriodicity)
 - Purpose (subjects/subject, with free keywords)
 - ParentIdentifier/inCollection (eop:parentIdentifier)

³ All the attributes presented in parenthesis in this general metadata layer belong to the DataCite metadata schema (<http://schema.datacite.org/>). Details on the usage of some of these properties can be also found, for the general metadata layer, at <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/>

-
- Status (eop:status)
 - Language (language)
 - Related Items (relatedItems/relatedItem)
 - **Credit, licensing and pricing layer**, which is also aligned as much as possible with the recommendations from OpenAIRE, and is also data cube and domain independent.
 - **Authors** (creators/creator)
 - Contributors (contributors/contributor)
 - **Publisher** (publisher)
 - Rights List (rightsList/rights)
 - Funding References (fundingReferences/fundingReference)
 - **Coverage metadata layer**, which allows representing those aspects related to the spatial and temporal coverage of the data cube, which are essential when looking for data cubes across domains.
 - Simple GeoLocation, for simple tools like CKAN and alike (according to DataCite, including geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPlace, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPoint, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationBox, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPolygon)
 - **Spatial coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, coordinate reference system).
 - **Temporal coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit).
 - Vertical coverage, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit).
 - No other dimensions are foreseen yet, although new use cases may bring additional dimensions.
 - **Data Acquisition and Product Information layer**, which allows representing those aspects related to the observations, processing levels, instruments, platforms, missions, etc. In general, for this metadata layer we will allow for the usage of general keywords (user-defined or associated to controlled lists) in the keywords section, so as to facilitate usage across domains.
 - **Keywords**
 - **Product type**
 - Product version
 - Data type
 - Data type unit
 - Size (sizes/size)
 - Format (formats/format)
 - Processing level
 - Processor
 - Instrument
 - Platform
 - Other Data Acquisition System
 - Data Quality
 - max**Value**
 - min**Value**
 - max**Date**
 - min**Date**
 - noData**Value**
 - Links to resources
 - Point of Contact

The second model is defined as an RO-Crate application profile to describe research objects in RELIANCE. The model includes:

- A general-purpose metadata model to describe research objects and its associated research artifacts. This model corresponds to the first two layers above, and it is covered by the core RO-crate specification.
- A general purpose models to describe data entities inside research objects, which defines the following properties (also covered by the core RO-crate specification). Note: In remainder of the document, we use the following prefixes:
 - sch: as shortcut of the schema.org namespace (<http://schema.org/>)
 - rel: as shortcut of the RELIANCE namespace (<http://w3id.org/earth-science/model#> - to be confirmed)
 - cm: as short of CodeMeta namespace (<https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>)

Table 1 General purpose metadata for data entities inside research objects

RELIANCE-RO Term	Constraint	Term type	Description
@id	MUST	data property	Identifier of the data entity
@type	MUST	object property	Type of data entity (e.g., File, Dataset, Workflow, etc.)
sch:name	MUST	data property	Name of the entity
sch:description	MUST	data property	Description of the entity
sch:contentSize	MAY	data property	Size of the content of the entity
sch:encodingFormat	MAY	data property	Encoding format used for the entity. It can be a string or a URL
sch:url	MAY	data property	URL with additional information about the entity
sch:distribution	MAY	object property	It leads to an entity of type sch:DataDownload
sch:identifier	MAY	object property	It leads to an entity of type sch:PropertyValue.

- A data cube metadata model to describe data cubes data entities in RELIANCE. This model corresponds to the third and fourth layer above, and defines the following properties:

Table 2 metadata elements for data cube data entities

RELIANCE-RO Term	Constraint	Term type	Description
@id	MUST	data property	URI Path relative to the RO Crate root, or an absolute URI, which point to a file with the data cube or to a Web service call that allows generating the data cube on demand
@type	MUST	object property	Array containing "File" and one of the following: DataCubeCollection, DataCubeProduct
sch:contentLocation	MAY	object property	Simple link to an entity that describes the location for this data cube
sch:temporalCoverage	MAY	data property	Simple description of the temporal coverage (e.g., 2011/2013)
rel:extent	MUST	data property	WKT description of the spatial object
rel:spatialStepResolution	MUST	data property	Resolution of observations

rel:coordinateReferenceSystem	MUST	data property	Coordinate reference system used for the WKT coordinates
sch:startTime	MUST	data property	Start time for the temporal coverage
sch:endTime	MUST	data property	End time for the temporal coverage
rel:temporalStepResolution	MUST	data property	Resolution (temporal) of the observations
rel:temporalReferenceSystem	MUST	data property	Temporal reference system, if different from the usual one
rel:highestElevation	MAY	data property	Value of the highest elevation
rel:lowestElevation	MAY	data property	Value of the lowest elevation
rel:verticalStepResolution	MAY	data property	Resolution (vertical) of the observations
rel:verticalReferenceSystem	MAY	data property	Vertical reference system, if different from the usual one (e.g., meters)
sch:keywords	MUST	data property	Keywords
sch:contentSize	MUST	data property	Size of the content of the entity
sch:encodingFormat	MUST	data property	Encoding format used for the entity. It can be a string or a URL
sch:contactPoint	MUST	object property	Link to an entity that acts as contact point for this data cube
rel:productType	MAY	data property	Type of product or collection
rel:productVersion	MAY	data property	Version of the product or collection
rel:dataType	MAY	data property	Type of the data for observations
rel:dataTypeUnit	MAY	data property	Unit for observations
rel:processingLevel	MAY	data property	Processing level
rel:processor	MAY	property	It may be a string or the id of the processor
rel:instrument	MAY	property	Same as above
rel:platform	MAY	property	Same as above
rel:otherDataAcquisitionSystem	MAY	property	Same as above
rel:dataQuality	MAY	data property	Any detail on the quality of data
rel:maxValue	MAY	data property	Maximum value for the observations
rel:minValue	MAY	data property	Minimum value for the observations
rel:noDataValue	MAY	data property	Value used in case that no data is available, as a way to represent null
rel:linksToResources	MAY	object property	Links to other relevant resources

- A software metadata model to describe research software data entities in RELIANCE. This model defines the following properties:

A Software Data Entity MUST include the following properties:

-
- @type: MUST be Software.
 - @id: MUST be either a URI Path relative to the RO Crate root, or an absolute URI, which can point to a file with the software, to a DOI with the software or to a Web address of the repository of the software.

A Software Data Entity SHOULD include the following properties:

- sch:name
- sch:description
- sch:license
- sch:softwareVersion
- sch:author
- sch:codeRepository
- cm:referencePublication

A Software Data Entity MAY include the following properties:

- cm:buildInstructions
- sch:programmingLanguage
- sch:runtimePlatform
- sch:downloadURL
- sch:operatingSystem
- sch:memoryRequirements
- sch:preprocessorRequirements
- sch:publisher
- cm:readme

Regarding the provision of keywords to optimize the possibilities for re-use, the research object model includes particular metadata elements for that, such as **purpose (subject)** and **keywords**, which can be associated to the research object itself or to the datasets (and any other product) it aggregates (e.g., data cubes and any other type of dataset used/produced).

Furthermore, research objects are enriched by the text mining RELIANCE service with additional metadata that is extracted from its descriptive metadata, as well as from the content of the resources it aggregates. The goal of this service is to enhance the research object findability by adding to the user-generated annotations new semantic metadata that is automatically gathered from research object content, more specifically from the resources containing textual content. This metadata comprise the main *concepts* found in resources containing text in the research object, the main *knowledge areas* in which these concepts are most frequently used, the main *expressions*, known in computational linguistics as noun phrases, found in the text, and *named entities* that are further classified in *people*, *organization* and *places*. The core of the semantic enrichment process is Expert System Cogito software. The classes used to annotate semantically the content are specified in the ContentDesc ontology⁴, and they are associated to the research object via the **subject** metadata element.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

Research data produced in RELIANCE will be open by default, and it will be made accessible by depositing it in public repositories, including:

- Open institutional repositories (e.g., INGV Data Portal, CNR-ISMAR resource catalogue)
- Open community specific repositories (e.g., Pangaea, EPOS Data Access Portal, CMIP6 Data Portal)

⁴ <http://everest.expertsystemlab.com/vocabulary/cdesc/index-en.html>

- Open catch-all repositories (e.g., Zenodo, B2Share)
- ROHub

Additionally, data cubes will be physically stored in data storage services/facilities (e.g., from RELIANCE partners (PSNC, MEEO) or from other EOSC providers (e.g., DICE, EGI)), while research objects will be stored in ROHub platform (one of the core RELIANCE services).

Regardless of the physical location of the data or data cubes, though, they will be managed and be accessible via the research objects in ROHub. Hence, research objects provide the method to access the datasets, while ROHub is the associated tool enabling such access. This also applies to other related research artifacts encapsulated in the research object, such as the methods and software used to process/generate the data, documentation about the data or investigation in general, or related publications in scholarly communication. Furthermore, research objects also include comprehensive metadata, not only about themselves (and their associated investigations), but also about the individual data entities they encapsulate, as described in the previous section. Notably, one of the properties of the metadata model is the license, which allows to specify the data entity license in machine readable format.

Additionally, if the datasets require specific tools to be able to use them, these can be also linked in the research object as software data entities and connected to the datasets with through a general ro-crate metadata element (**softwareRequirements**). Similarly, if needed, documentation can be easily associated to the tool entity via a software metadata element (**referencePublication**), as described in Section 4.1, or via a general ro-crate metadata element (**documentation**).

Since research communities expect their research data to be open default, at least so far, there is no need at this moment for a data access committee that would need to decide whether and how datasets will be shared. However, this may change in the future if such expectations change in the next phases of the project.

4.3 Making data interoperable

RELIANCE will follow, as much as possible, existing standards for data formats and metadata vocabularies to make data interoperable and ensure compliance. For example, the data produced by RELIANCE includes, among others (with their data formats):

- EO data derived by: scientific literature review; recording of acoustic data and environmental variables and their processing, e.g., underwater noise and bathymetry (formats: ascii, csv, txt, GeoTIFF, shapefile); SAR interferometric processing, i.e., ground velocity maps and time series of deformation (formats: shapefile, csv, GeoTIFF, text file); Volcanic Plume Retrieval (VPR) algorithm (formats: NetCDF, ASCII, GeoTIFF); and other EO data such as Sentinel-3 OLCI, SPOT/VEGETATION, PROBAV;
- simulation and/or analysis data such as model outputs, e.g., FLEXPART, HYSPLIT, LAGRANTO, CESM, NorESM (formats: NetCDF, GRIB2);
- data cubes of satellite imageries, such as Sentinel-3 SLSTR, NASA MODIS, EUMETSAT SEVIRI. Input data managed by data cubes can be in different formats like NetCDF, HDF or GeoTIFF, and the format of the final data cube is GeoTIFF
- Research objects, which can be serialized and exchanged as ro-crates or zipped files based on the original ro-model

In any case, as previously mentioned, regardless of the type of data generated, it will be managed and be accessible via the research objects in ROHub. And, as described in Section 4.1, research objects are described with a rich set of metadata, both at the research object level and at the level of the data entities it aggregates.

Moreover, as described in Section 4.1, the metadata model for research objects is defined as an RO-Crate application profile. RO-crate uses JSON-LD⁵ to express the metadata using linked data, describing data resources as well as contextual entities such as people, organizations, software and equipment as a series of linked JSON-LD objects - using common published vocabularies, chiefly schema.org⁶ (which is well documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers). So, RELIANCE application profile builds on top that, reusing schema.org as the base metadata standard, and extends it with metadata elements from other commonly used vocabularies (e.g., CodeMeta that extends schema.org with additional properties relevant in research software projects) plus additional metadata elements defined in a RELIANCE specific vocabulary (mostly allowing the description of the novel data cubes data entities dealt in RELIANCE). Moreover, the RELIANCE application profile includes mappings to the original Research Object model, which was based mostly on Dublin Core terms⁷ for the generic metadata and the RO suite of ontologies⁸ and extensions⁹. Finally, as described in Section 4.1, the metadata extracted by the text mining RELIANCE service, is represented according to the ContentDesc ontology¹⁰.

Using JSON-LD and standard FAIR vocabularies for the representation and description of research objects and its aggregated entities, allows them to interoperate at Web-scale.

4.4 Increase data re-use

One of the main goals of RELIANCE project is to foster and promote the widest possible reusability of the data produced. This requires a deep knowledge of both content and provenance of data sets as well as an accurate understanding of their license, which should be reflected and properly represented in the associated metadata. Some points that should be addressed by such metadata include for instance, the purpose, the date of creation, modification and publication, the version, the language and the license. All of these, and other relevant metadata are covered by the research object metadata model based on RO-crate, as described in more detail in D5.1.

Regarding the license, the data produced in RELIANCE will be released by default under the CC-BY 4.0 license¹¹. At this point, our user communities do not envision datasets or other results that will need to be kept closed, but this is a continuous analysis, so in the next iteration of the DMP we will update these aspects if needed.

As mentioned above, regardless of the type of data or other results generated, they will be managed and be accessible via the research objects in ROHub. Research objects are public by default in ROHub (anybody can see/download/reuse them), so as soon as scientists start creating their research objects and aggregating resources, they will be publicly available. ROHub allows to create private research objects, though, in order to allow only selected people to read/write them. So, in few cases, scientists may start working on a private research object, and will make it public only after reaching some milestone. In any case, the datasets and other results produced will be reusable by other scientists within and across research communities. In fact, one of the key long-term goals of RELIANCE is to promote and support multidisciplinary research, where results from one community may be found relevant and reused in another one only thanks to RELIANCE services.

⁵ <https://json-ld.org/>

⁶ <https://schema.org/>

⁷ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

⁸ <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro/>

⁹ <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro/tree/earth-science>

¹⁰ <http://everest.expertsystemlab.com/vocabulary/cdesc/index-en.html>

¹¹ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Regarding the availability of the data and other results, the goal is that RELIANCE services providing access to it will be available via EOSC marketplace way beyond the project. ROHub, for example, is a service that has been up and running for almost 10 years, and is a key service of the PSNC portfolio that will be maintained and supported after the project in the long-term. Similarly, ADAM for accessing and using data cubes is one of the main products of MEE0, which they plan to support and maintain/extend after RELIANCE. Additionally, RELIANCE leverages other EOSC services via ROHub, such as Zenodo, B2Share and B2Drop, where data and other results produced may be also stored and published, so that it remains accessible in the future.

Finally, ROHub includes quality assessment functionalities, allowing the scientists to verify that their research objects include the minimal set of resources and metadata that would enable their discovery and reuse in a particular community or application. Such quality parameters may assess the quality of the research object in terms of its content, or they can specify the required metadata at the level of the research object or at the level of the aggregated resources (e.g., datasets). Moreover, such quality parameters can be monitored continuously over time, in order to identify decay situations where some of the resources aggregated, for example, are not accessible anymore.

5 Allocation of Resources

Allocation of resources means the cost of making the produced research data FAIR, i.e., findable, accessible, Interoperable and re-useable, in a project. The cost may be different depending on the datasets considered to be used and accessed.

RELIANCE project provides to researchers with virtual access to the research infrastructures they need for their research work. This includes the costs of providing them with access to RELIANCE services, which are the ones necessary to make the produced research data and other results FAIR. In RELIANCE such research infrastructure is provided by PSNC to the rest of the consortium, and the costs of the virtual access are declared on the basis of actual costs, which are covered in the project under the budget of WP6 - EOSC Integration and Service Offering. Furthermore, as some of the data and results produced by RELIANCE will be stored in other EOSC services, the costs of keeping them available and FAIR is out of the scope of the project. In any case, for researchers the access to the data/results will be free of cost.

Additionally, PSNC as infrastructure provider, ROHub service provider and project coordinator is the main responsible of the high-level data management in the RELIANCE project; however, all the other partners of RELIANCE will contribute to it. For example, research communities must always analyse and decide if there are any particular limitations/constraints imposed by their internal policies for the produced research data/results that would require to treat them differently (e.g., not releasing them publicly as by default).

The long-term preservation of the RELIANCE datasets (also involving data cubes and research objects) from the various use case scenarios also involves resource allocation and is also an important aspect of the data management plan. In the case of RELIANCE project, as discussed above regardless of the physical location of the data or data cubes, they will be managed and be accessible via the research objects in ROHub, which supports their long-term preservation (including quality monitoring). The associated costs are covered via the virtual access as described above. The individual resources (e.g., datasets), though, may be kept in different repositories as previously discussed, which may have their own long-term preservation policies. Accordingly, data providers will be responsible for datasets they produce, especially those that they keep in external services/repositories. The recommendation,

though, is to rely on established repositories (e.g., institutional, EOSC services) which takes the preservation into account.

6 Data Security & Ethical Aspects

Data security is vital for data protection throughout the project. The data management plan should provide information about the recovery, storage and transfer of sensitive data, particularly from the RELIANCE case studies.

In RELIANCE all the case studies related datasets, data cubes and research objects may be stored in different repositories. For example, research objects, they will be stored in ROHub in a high-security environment, particularly, PSNC's PaaS environment configured with daily backups having 7 days TTL (time to live). Additionally, as previously noted, ROHub gives the possibility to restrict read/write access to research objects if needed. In the case of data cubes, they will be stored also in high-security environments, e.g., data storage infrastructure provided by PSNC or by other EOSC data storage service providers, which have clear policies for the long-term preservation and curation of data. And regarding the particular datasets and other resources produced they may be stored in different repositories, but the recommendation, as previously mentioned, is to use established and certified repositories (e.g., institutional, EOSC services) with clear policies for long-term preservation and curation. No sensitive data has been identified for the research data used/produced.

The ethical aspects come into consideration when dealing with and sharing personal data. RELIANCE project is aware of and bound to follow the EU and national legislation and policies referring to protecting personal data and privacy. The RELIANCE consortium is committed to take all the necessary measures to ensure that all project activities comply with the European Charter of Fundamental rights¹² and all data protection relevant EU regulations.

To ensure appropriate protection of the data, RELIANCE project will implement and adapt, if needed, EU procedures/regulations particularly regarding the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for data protection¹³, and the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data¹⁴.

In particular, in RELIANCE, these procedures/regulations concern the user/personal data collected by the ROHub platform. As mentioned in Section 3, though, which particular data is collected and how it is handled is described in the ROHub privacy policy, which must be consented by the user in order to create his account.

Furthermore, as described in the ROHub privacy policy, we have appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO), whom can be contact regarding the protection of the users' personal data and the exercise of the users' rights by e-mail, phone or in writing.

7 Datasets

The tables below provide a summary of the datasets already identified to be (re)used/collected or produced by the RELIANCE use cases. The datasets are grouped by use case/challenge. This list will be

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/info/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/eu-charter-fundamental-rights_en

¹³ <https://gdpr.eu/tag/gdpr/>

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

continuously updated, and a more complete set of datasets (and other products) per use case will be presented in D7.1 in M12. This list also does not include the initial set of data cubes that have been or are being created, which are presented in D4.3 delivered in parallel to this document.

In general, the dataset type can be one of the three categories below, although in the tables below only RO and DS are used (as explained above):

- RO – Research Object
- DC – Data Cube
- DS – Any other dataset

7.1 Multidisciplinary case studies on 2020 lockdown use case

7.1.1 Scenario 1: “Bibliography analysis on lockdown related papers within Earth science”

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC0-SC1	Scientific papers	DS	Web of science portal	Collection of scientific papers about lockdown in marine sciences	excel file (.xls)	~300 KB	Documentation is in the form of open access papers e.g., pdf format
RO1-GC0-SC1	RO1 GC0 SC1	RO	ROhub	Bibliographic RO for scientific paper, with a short description and content based annotations.	Bibliographic RO	TBA ¹⁵	Documentation is in the form of open access papers e.g., pdf format
RO2-GC0-SC1	RO2 GC0 SC1	RO	ROhub	Bibliographic RO integrating all the collected scientific papers	Bibliographic RO	TBA	Documentation is in the form of open access papers e.g., pdf format

7.1.2 Scenario 2: Marine Monitoring during the Anthropause

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC0-SC2	Questionnaire	DS	Online ¹⁶	Questionnaire aiming to understand the (de-)impact of the lockdown on marine coastal and atmospheric environments networking with other organizations in Europe focusing on initiatives devoted to this assessment.	URL	< 5KB	
RO1-GC0-SC2	Marine Monitoring during the Anthro pause ¹⁷	RO	ROhub	This RO collects information on efforts to monitor the reduction of human impact on Mediterranean marine ecosystems due to the lockdowns that took place in different countries during 2020-2021 ("Anthro pause")	Basic RO	40 MB	Documentation includes Bibliography, Questionnaire, News, Websites

7.1.3 Scenario 3: Impact of the Covid-19 Lockdown on Air quality

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC0-SC3	CAMS European air quality forecasts	DS	Data available for download from CAMS Atmosphere Data Store	Daily (hourly) air quality analyses for the european domain (about 10 km horizontal resolution). The analysis combines model data (from 9 different models) with observations	GRIB2/ NetCDF	TBA	All the available variables will be available as Data Cube. Time of

¹⁵ To be analyzed

¹⁶ https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe9yaL-IV4bLW41sc482YxxV-TKYP6WtLK7iTVehgWORTTarg/viewform?usp=sf_link

¹⁷ http://www.rohub.org/rodetails/Lockdown_20_21/overview

			(ADS), but, it will be accessed via Data Cubes	provided by the European Environment Agency (EEA) into a complete and consistent dataset using various data assimilation.			interest: july 2018 to 2021
RO1-GC0-SC3	Bibliography on air quality during and after lockdown	RO	ROHub	Bibliography on air quality during and after lockdown	Bibliographic RO	TBA	Documentation includes Bibliography, Questionnaire, News, Websites
RO2-GC0-SC3	RO2 GC0 SC3	RO	ROHub	This scenario plans to produce one data cube RO which will be described in more detail in the next version of the DMP	Datacube RO	TBA	
DS2-GC0-SC3	Air quality Indices	DS	TBA	Compute air quality indices	table (.xls, .csv)	TBA	
RO2-GC0-SC3	Galaxy Workflow for air quality analysis	RO	ROHub	Galaxy workflow for getting air quality indices from CADS on a given location	Workflow RO	TBA	
DS3-GC0-SC3	Local measurements of air quality	DS	TBA	Get timeseries from stations and for closest locations of interest	table (.xls, .csv)	TBA	
RO3-GC0-SC3	RO3 GC0 SC3	RO	ROHub	Generate report (Jupyter notebook) from running RO workflow on a given location and for specific dates.	Workflow RO	TBA	

7.1.4 Scenario 4: Analysis from satellite data – Environmental monitoring from space

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC0-SC4	Satellite Dataset	DS	Sentinel3-OLCI/Meris	This dataset involves collection and analyses of satellite products	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.
DS2-GC0-SC4	NRT satellite products	DS		This dataset involves collection and analyses of satellite products	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.
DS3-GC0-SC4	Satellite maps	DS		This dataset involves collection and analyses of satellite products	TBA	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.

Additionally, this scenario plans to produce several research objects, including 2 data cubes research objects and one basic research object, which will be described in more detail in the next version of the DMP.

7.1.5 Scenario 5: Underwater Sound Pressure Level Analysis

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC0-SC5	WAV Dataset	DS	Raw wav files are collected through hydrophone, extracted and stored into a local server	Dataset including collection of raw wav files from hydrophone memories and storage of raw wav files into a server.	Raw wav files	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.
DS2-GC0-SC5	SPL Dataset	DS	Server	The SPL dataset consists of .csv files downloaded from SPL files and obtained from ANP app.	text file (.csv)	TBA	Associated documentation involves technical documents.

DS3-GC0-SC5	Graphs	DS	TBA	Images generated by python code	Images	TBA	Associated documentation involves technical notes and documents
RO1-GC0-SC5	RO SPL	RO	ROhub	RO with workflow	Workflow w RO	TBA	Involves technical documentation

7.2 Grand Challenge 2: Loss of Biodiversity and Sustainability (Biodiversity, fisheries, marine litter) use case

7.2.1 Scenario 1: Mapping the Mediterranean photic zone

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC2-SC1	Scientific Literature	DS	The literature review is performed on Google Scholar, Scopus and Web of Science database.	Scientific publications from peer-reviewed journals reporting thresholds for photic metabolisms ¹⁸	Text files (.pdf)	3 MB	Licensed under journals data policy
DS2-GC2-SC1	Surface PAR, Chl-a and Kd ₄₉₀ Data	DS	https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/	NetCDF data on marine surface PAR light, Chl-a and Kd490 for the Mediterranean Sea accessible from NASA Ocean Color repository	NetCDF	TBA	Documentations: https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/atbd/par/ , https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/atbd/chlor_a/ , https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/atbd/kd_490/
RO1-GC2-SC1	RO1 GC2 SC1	RO	ROHub	Bibliographic RO integrating all the collected scientific papers about light penetration in the water column	Bibliographic RO	TBA	
RO2-GC2-SC1	RO2 GC2 SC1	RO	ROHub	Data cube RO integrating the environmental data required to model the penetration of light along the water column	Data cube RO	TBA	
RO3-GC2-SC1	RO3 GC2 SC1	RO	ROHub	Research Object to share the Jupyter Notebook containing the model script	Workflow RO	TBA	
RO4-GC2-SC1	Mapping the Mediterranean photic zone	RO	ROHub	Basic RO including the entire cross-disciplinary experiment	Basic RO	TBA	
DS3-GC2-SC1	Shapefile of the photic zone	DS	The shapefile is created through Workflow RO	Spatial extension of the photic zone in the Mediterranean Sea	Shape files (.shp)	730 MB	The resource is still unpublished, but it will be included in a RO and uploaded in Zenodo/Github

7.3 Grand Challenge 3: Extreme weather events and climate adaptation (biomass) use case

7.3.1 Scenario 1: Spatial and temporal distribution of CWC in the Mediterranean Sea

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC3-SC1	Coral database	DS	Scopus (Public and local datasets) https://www.pangaea.de/ https://github.com/	Local datasets contain information (e.g. lat, long, depth) of cold-water coral sites in the Mediterranean Sea, as described in oceanographic cruise reports or literature data. These information can be transferred to online repositories (e.g. Pangaea, GitHub)	TBA	TBA	The resource could be included in a RO and uploaded in Zenodo/Github

¹⁸ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09670260801979303>

DS2-GC3-SC1	Environmental dataset	DS	Public and local datasets	Climatological fields (temperature, salinity, nutrients, dissolved oxygen concentration) for the Mediterranean Sea at different water depths in NetCDF format.	NetCDF	TBA	Documentations https://marine.copernicus.eu/ https://www.seadatanet.org/worldoceanatlas
DS3-GC3-SC1	Fossil coral age	DS	Internal or external laboratory	The fossil coral samples will be analysed for U/Th and ¹⁴ C using mass spectrometry. Results will be processed using dedicated software available online to obtain accurate coral ages	TBA	TBA	Documentation: https://www.ucl.ac.uk/~ucfbpve/isoplotr/home/index.html http://calib.org/calib/
DS4-GC3-SC1	Coral-based reconstructions	DS	Scopus and R scripts	Geochemical data will be converted to environmental information using established calibration equations from literature and available R scripts	R scripts	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.
DS5-GC3-SC1	Scientific literature	DS	Scopus https://www.pangaea.de/ https://github.com/	Scientific publications from peer-reviewed journals reporting paleoceanographic reconstructions in the Mediterranean Sea	TBA	TBA	Documentation includes paper, technical notes, presentation documents, grant description and regulations etc.
DS6-GC3-SC1	Med-CORDEX simulations	DS	https://www.medcordex.eu/	Assembly of regional climate models having outputs of historical simulations and multiple RPC future scenarios provided in NetCDF via THREDDS DATA SERVER	NetCDF	TBA	THREDDS DATA SERVER
DS7-GC3-SC1	Model output post-processing	DS	Personal data process	Future scenarios of coral distribution based on Med-CORDEX simulations using software for scientific analysis and visualization	TBA	TBA	The resource could be included in a RO and uploaded in Zenodo/Github
DS8-GC3-SC1	Environmental Niche Modeling (ENM)	DS	R Core Team; GIS software	Coral occurrences and future climatic scenarios will be used to develop Environmental Niche Models to predict the future distribution of corals in raster layer format	Raster layer format	TBA	The resource will be included in a RO and uploaded in Zenodo/Github where metadata will be freely accessible.

7.3.2 Scenario 2: Reindeer husbandry in the changing climate

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC3-SC2	Arctic regional reanalysis for Europe	DS	Copernicus Climate Change Data Store (C3S) ¹⁹	The C3S Arctic Regional Reanalysis (CARRA) dataset contains 3-hourly analyses and hourly short-term forecasts of atmospheric and surface meteorological variables (surface and near-surface temperature, surface and top of atmosphere fluxes, precipitation, cloud, humidity, wind, pressure, snow and sea variables) at 2.5 km resolution. East Domain. Variables: albedo, snow density, surface thermal radiation downward,	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products ²⁰

¹⁹ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-carra-single-levels?tab=overview>

²⁰ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-carra-single-levels?tab=form>

				surface solar radiation downwards, total precipitation, 2m temperature, orography, snow depth water equivalent. Period: 1998 to 2019			
DS2-GC3-SC2	ECMWF seasonal forecast	DS	Copernicus Climate change Data Store (C3S) ²¹	Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels. Area: 68N-15E to 71.5N-32E. Variables: snow depth, temperature (2 meter) and precipitation (rain or freezing rain/drizzle). Period: Forecast years (2017 to 2021)	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products
DS3-GC3-SC2	ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis	DS	Copernicus Climate change Data Store (C3S) ²²	ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis. Area: 68N-15E to 71.5N-32E. Variables: snow depth, snow density, surface solar radiation downwards, temperature (2 meter) and precipitation (rain or freezing rain/drizzle). Period: From 1950	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products
DS4-GC3-SC2	Timeseries from Norwegian Meteorological stations	DS	Norwegian Meteorological Institute ²³	Meteorological Institute data (temperature, precipitation, etc.)	txt/NetCDF/csv	TBA	Documentation is in the form of open access papers e.g., pdf format

7.3.3 Scenario 3: Arctic browning and winter warming

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC3-SC3	UERRA regional reanalysis for Europe	DS	Copernicus Climate change Service (C3S) ²⁴	Regional reanalysis covering a large period of time e.g., from 1961 to 2019 with variable: snow density, snow depth water equivalent, 2m temperature, skin temperature, total precipitation, albedo, orography, total cloud cover. Area of interest: Norway. Single level (surface)	GRIB2/NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products
DS2-GC3-SC3	NDVI Index	DS	Copernicus Global Land service. (Sentinel-3 and PROBA-V) ²⁵	Vegetation assessment. Area of interest: Norway. Period: past to present (from 1999). Sentinel-3 (from 2020) and PROBA-V (from 2016) with high resolution and from 2019 with low resolution (1km)	NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products
DS3-GC3-SC3	Land cover classification	DS	Land cover classification gridded maps from 1992 to present derived from satellite observations ²⁶	This dataset provides global maps describing the land surface into 22 classes, which have been defined using the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization's (UN FAO) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS). In addition to the land cover (LC) maps, four quality flags are produced to document the reliability of the classification and change detection. Area of interest: Norway. Period: 1992 to 2020	NetCDF	TBA	License to use Copernicus Products

²¹ [https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/search?text=&type=dataset&keywords=\({"Product type: Seasonal forecasts"}\)](https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/search?text=&type=dataset&keywords=({)

²² <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/search?text=ERA5%20back%20extension&type=dataset>

²³ <https://www.met.no/en/free-meteorological-data/Download-services>

²⁴ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-uerra-europe-single-levels?tab=form>

²⁵ <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/ndvi>

²⁶ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-land-cover?tab=overview>

7.3.4 Scenario 4: Impact of climate extremes on vegetation dynamics in multiple dynamic vegetation models and their future projections

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC3-SC4	ISIMIP2b climate variables to detect extremes and response variables from ecosystem models.	DS	Downloaded from https://data.isi mip.org and made publicly available at https://galaxy-minio.uiogeo-apps.sigma2.no/	Data from the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project. ISIMIP2b corresponds to simulation for assessing the impacts of 1.5 °C global warming. Area of interest: 40-90 N, 0-360 E. Time: historical 1981-2005; future 2080-2100 from rcp26 and rcp85. Climate variables of interest to detect extremes: surface temperature, precipitation, soil moisture & temperature, snow depth, surface humidity & wind,	NetCDF	TBA	Licenses used in ISIMIP2B can be found at https://www.isimip.org/gettingstarted/terms-of-use/licenses-publicly-available-isimip-data/?query=license#licences-used-in-isimip2b

7.4 Grand Challenge 4: Reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions use case

7.4.1 Scenario 1: Analysis of surface deformations at active volcanoes

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC1	RO1 GC4 SC1	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the selection of InSAR images spanning 2015-2021 related to the Campi Flegrei caldera (Italy)	Data RO	TBA	
RO1-GC4-SC1	RO2 GC4 SC1	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the results of the InSAR multi-temporal data processing on the Campi Flegrei area during 2015-2021. The results are mean ground velocity maps and displacement time-series.	Data RO	TBA	

7.4.2 Scenario 2: Models of volcanic plumbing system

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC2	RO1 GC4 SC2	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the run of the VSM tool with description and metadata. The code is for Jupyter Notebooks.	Code RO	TBA	

7.4.3 Scenario 3: Mapping emissions of volcanic eruptions from space

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC3	RO1 GC4 SC3	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the selection of MODIS/SLSTR images related to the AOI (area of interest) and TOI (time of interest)	Data RO	TBA	
RO2-GC4-SC3	RO2 GC4 SC3	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the results of the VPR data processing related to the AOI (area of interest) and TOI (time of interest). The results are AOD, Mass maps of SO ₂ , ash and ice.	Data RO	TBA	

7.4.4 Scenario 4: Massive RO scenario: Imaging plumes from an erupting volcano

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC4	RO1 GC4 SC4	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the selection of SEVIRI images related to the AOI (area of interest) during 2021 February-March Etna volcanic eruptions.	Data RO	TBA	

7.4.5 Scenario 5: Massive RO scenario: VONA bulletins

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC5	RO1 GC4 SC5	RO	ROhub	This RO contains the report by INGV on the VONA alert of ash cloud emission for Italian volcanoes: Mt Etna and Stromboli.	Bibliographic RO	TBA	Documentation is in the form of reports in pdf format

7.4.6 Scenario 6: Massive & automatic RO scenario: INGV Bulletin of Italian Volcanoes

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
RO1-GC4-SC6	RO1 GC4 SC6	RO	ROhub	The RO contains the report as pdf of the state of activity of a given week at Mt Etna or Stromboli (Italy).	Bibliographic RO	TBA	Documentation is in the form of reports in pdf format

7.4.7 Scenario 7: RO scenario: seismic data (events) from INGV catalogues

Id	Name	Type	Source	Description	Format	Size	Other
DS1-GC4-SC7	Seismic catalogue	DS	http://terremoti.invgv.it/en	Catalogue of worldwide seismic events (INGV/USGS)	pdf	TBA	http://terremoti.invgv.it/en/webservices_and_software https://earthquake.usgs.gov/fdsnws/event/1/
RO1-GC4-SC7	Seismic sequence	RO	ROHub	This RO contains dataset of seismic events, clustered per region of interest, temporal interval and predetermined magnitudes and depths, aiming at identify specific case studies in seismic or volcanic areas, that can contribute to surface deformation	Bibliographic RO	TBA	